

Synthesis and characterization of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets

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Abstract : A series of novel 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets have been synthesized by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide with various aryl isothiocyanates. The newly synthesized compounds have been characterized by analytical and IR, ^1H NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Maltosyl isothiocarbamide, aryl isothiocyanates, isodithiobiurets.

Introduction

Natural products show a broad spectrum of biological activities with a high potential for medicinal applications. Carbohydrates are also structurally important component of such numerous biologically active natural products. Some of its *N* and *S*-linked sugar derivatives exhibiting antifungal¹, antitumor², anticancer³, antiviral⁴ and anti-malarial activity⁵. Recently, *ortho* carbonyl glycosides used for the treatment of cancer by boron neutron capture therapy⁶. Such significant and diversified pharmaceutical values of glycosides have focused our interest on the studies towards the disaccharide moiety. Our present invention relates to synthesis of several *N*-linked maltose derivatives via the most powerful intermediate maltosyl isothiocyanate⁷⁻¹⁰. This is potent irreversible inhibitors of glucose transport in human erythrocytes¹¹. In order to illustrate the synthetic potential we have developed a new synthetic method in which 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (3) was readily transformed into the corresponding 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (5a-g) (Scheme 2) on reaction with various aryl isothiocyanates (4a-g). The required 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (3) (Scheme 1) was obtained by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl thio-carbamide (1) with benzyl chloride (2).

Results and discussion

Several 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (5a-g) (Scheme 2) were prepared by the reaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (3) with various alkyl isothiocyanates (4a-g) in benzene. After condensation, the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky residue. This residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid (5a-g). The products were found to be desulphurized when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution. In spectral analysis¹²⁻¹⁴, IR spectrum of product shows bands due to Ar-H, N-H, aliphatic C-H, C=O, C-O, C=N, C-N, C=S, C-S stretching and the ^1H NMR spectrum of product distinctly displayed signals due to aromatic protons, maltose ring protons and NH protons. The Mass spectrum of product was also observed.

Experimental

General procedure :

Melting points determined are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Nujol, KBr on a FT-IR Perkin-Elmer RXI (4000–450 cm^{-1}) spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR measurements were performed on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as internal reference. The mass spectra FAB were recorded on a JEOL SX-102 Mass spectrometer. Optical rotation $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ measured on a Equip-Tronics

Scheme 1

where, Bz = COC₆H₅ (benzyl)

R = (a) Phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Scheme 2

Digital Polarimeter EQ-800 at 31 °C in CHCl₃. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on silica gel G for TLC (Merck) and spots were visualized by iodine vapour.

Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl-S-benzyl isothiobarbamide (3) :

A mixture of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl thiocarbamide (1) (3.5 g, 0.003 M) and benzyl chloride (2) (0.39 mL, 0.003 M) in ethanol (40 mL) was refluxed for 3 h. The completion of the reaction was confirmed by TLC. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice cold ammonium hydroxide solution. The white colour solid separated out was filtered off and finally recrystallized with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) (3) (3.3 g, 87.53%), m.p. 115–120 °C (Scheme 1).

Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl-5-*p*-tolyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (5a-g) (Scheme 2) :

A reaction mixture of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-maltosyl-S-benzyl isothiobarbamide (3) (2.5 g, 0.002 M) and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (4g) (0.30 g, 0.002 M) in benzene (30 mL) was heated under reflux for 6 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain sticky residue. This residue was triturated

with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a granular pale yellow solid (5g). The crude product was purified by chloroform-ether and recrystallized by ethanol-water (2.1 g, 75%), m.p. 144 °C (Scheme 2).

The physical and spectral characterization results are summarized below (5a-g). The compounds (5a-g) were prepared according to the above mentioned method.

5a : Yield 2.3 g (83.03%); m.p. 134–137 °C; [α]_D³¹ + 79.55° (c, 1.00 in CHCl₃); R_f 0.81 (1 : 1, petroleum ether : EtOAc); IR (KBr) : ν 3451.9 (N-H), 3066.7 (Ar-H), 2961 (ali. C-H), 1728.6 (C=O), 1584.5 (C=N), 1371 (C-N), 1271.3 (C-O), 1176 (C=S), 1096.5–1028.2 and 938.1 (characteristic of maltose), 772.2 (C-S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ in ppm, CDCl₃) : δ 8.52–7.22 (45H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 2C₆H₅), 6.14–6.10 (1H, m, N-H), 5.67–3.90 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S-CH₂), 5.27 (1H, s, N-H); FABMS (*m/z*) : 1355 (M⁺+2), 1353 (M⁺), 1264 (M⁺+2-C₇H₅O), 1220 (M⁺+2-C₈H₇O₂), 1115 (M⁺+2-C₈H₇O₂, C₇H₅O), 1053 (HBM⁺=M-C₁₅H₁₄N₃S₂), 976 (HBM-C₆H₅), 948 (HBM-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBM-C₇H₅O₂), 918 (HBM-C₈H₇O₂), 827 (C₇H₅O, C₈H₇O₂), 579 (TBG⁺=HBM-C₂₇H₂₂O₈), 474 (TBG-C₆H₅), 353 (TBG-C₇H₅O, C₇H₅O₂), 232 (HBM-TBG, 2C₇H₅O₂), 135 (C₈H₇O₂⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) (Found : C, 65.99; H, 4.55; N, 3.02; S, 4.76. Calcd. for

$C_{76}H_{63}O_{17}N_3S_2$ requires : C, 66.04; H, 4.65; N, 3.10; S, 4.73%.

5b : Yield 1.8 g (63.38%); m.p. 131–132 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ -1.88° (c, 1.00 in $CHCl_3$); R_f 0.62 (1 : 1, petroleum ether : EtOAc) (Found : C, 65.70; H, 4.43; N, 3.00; S, 4.69. Calcd. for $C_{76}H_{62}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$ requires : C, 65.75; H, 4.47; N, 3.02; S, 4.61%).

5c : Yield 1.5 g (52.81%); m.p. 136–138 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ -84.40° (c, 1.00 in $CHCl_3$); R_f 0.56 (1 : 1, petroleum ether : EtOAc); IR (KBr) : ν 3477.2 (N–H), 3066.3 (Ar–H), 2962.6 (ali. C–H), 1728.5 (C=O), 1584.3 (C=N), 1374.1 (C–N), 1271.7 (C–O), 1176 (C=S), 1096.3–1027.6 and 938.3 (characteristic of maltose), 772 (C–S) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (δ in ppm, $CDCl_3$) : δ 8.11–7.20 (44H, m, $7COC_6H_5$, C_6H_5 , C_6H_4), 6.16–6.08 (1H, m, N–H), 5.79–4.24 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S– CH_2), 5.69 (1H, s, N–H); FABMS (m/z) : 1387 (M^+), 1352 ($M^+ - Cl$), 1147 ($M - C_7H_5O$, $C_8H_7O_2$), 1053 ($HBM^+ = M - C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2Cl$), 976 ($HBM - C_6H_5$), 948 ($HBM - C_7H_5O$), 932 ($HBM - C_7H_5O_2$), 918 ($HBM - C_8H_7O_2$), 827 (C_7H_5O , $C_8H_7O_2$), 579 ($TBG^+ = HBM - C_{27}H_{22}O_8$), 474 ($TBG - C_6H_5$), 353 ($TBG - C_7H_5O$, $C_7H_5O_2$), 232 ($HBM - TBG$, $2C_7H_5O_2$), 135 ($C_8H_7O_2^+$), 105 ($C_7H_5O^+$), 77 ($C_6H_5^+$) (Found : C, 65.71; H, 4.42; N, 2.99; S, 4.64. Calcd. for $C_{76}H_{62}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$ requires : C, 65.75; H, 4.47; N, 3.02; S, 4.61%).

5d : Yield 2.0 g (70.42%); m.p. 129–130 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ $+67.82^\circ$ (c, 1.00 in $CHCl_3$); R_f 0.80 (1 : 1, petroleum ether : EtOAc) (Found : C, 65.61; H, 4.31; N, 2.90; S, 4.69. Calcd. for $C_{76}H_{62}O_{17}N_3S_2Cl$ requires : C, 65.75; H, 4.47; N, 3.02; S, 4.61%).

5e : Yield 1.44 g (51.42%); m.p. 138–141 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ -81.70° (c, 1.00 in $CHCl_3$); R_f 0.70 (6 : 4, petroleum ether : EtOAc) (Found : C, 67.48; H, 4.68; N, 3.03; S, 4.66. Calcd. for $C_{77}H_{65}O_{17}N_3S_2$ requires : C, 67.59; H, 4.75; N, 3.07; S, 4.68%).

5f : Yield 2.6 g (92.85%); m.p. 132–133 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ $+121.5^\circ$ (c, 1.00 in $CHCl_3$); R_f 0.62 (6 : 4, petroleum ether : EtOAc) (Found : C, 67.58; H, 4.76; N, 3.06; S, 4.69. Calcd. for $C_{77}H_{65}O_{17}N_3S_2$ requires : C, 67.59; H, 4.75; N, 3.07; S, 4.68%).

5g : Yield 2.1 g (75%); m.p. 144 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ $+174.1^\circ$ (c, 1.00 in $CHCl_3$); R_f 0.80 (6 : 4, petroleum ether :

EtOAc); IR (KBr) : ν 3450 (N–H), 3066.8 (Ar–H), 2960.5 (ali. C–H), 1728.8 (C=O), 1584.5 (C=N), 1374.4 (C–N), 1271.3 (C–O), 1176 (C=S), 1096.8–1028.4 and 938.1 (characteristic of maltose), 772.7 (C–S) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (δ in ppm, $CDCl_3$) : δ 8.58–7.22 (45H, m, $7COC_6H_5$, C_6H_5 , C_6H_4), 6.14–6.08 (1H, m, N–H), 5.64–3.90 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S– CH_2), 4.77 (1H, s, N–H), 2.34 (3H, s, Ar– CH_3); FABMS (m/z) : 1367 (M^+), 1352 ($M^+ - CH_3$), 1276 ($M - CH_2C_6H_5$), 1076 ($M - 2C_8H_7O_2$), 1053 ($HBM^+ = M - C_{16}H_{16}N_3S_2$), 976 ($HBM - C_6H_5$), 948 ($HBM - C_7H_5O$), 932 ($HBM - C_7H_5O_2$), 918 ($HBM - C_8H_7O_2$), 827 (C_7H_5O , $C_8H_7O_2$), 579 ($TBG^+ = HBM - C_{27}H_{22}O_8$), 474 ($TBG - C_6H_5$), 353 ($TBG - C_7H_5O$, $C_7H_5O_2$), 232 ($HBM - TBG$, $2C_7H_5O_2$), 135 ($C_8H_7O_2^+$), 105 ($C_7H_5O^+$), 77 ($C_6H_5^+$) (Found : C, 67.53; H, 4.60; N, 3.05; S, 4.78. Calcd. for $C_{77}H_{65}O_{17}N_3S_2$ requires : C, 67.59; H, 4.75; N, 3.07; S, 4.68%).

$HBM^+ =$ Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl, $TBG^+ =$ Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucosyl.

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